

Fig. D.1. Cumulative number distributions of the bound particles to the NSC as a function of the stars orbital parameters r_{per} and e_{orb} with different velocity reduction factors for NGC 6401, HP 1 and 6681. Dark violet – $V_{\text{red}} = 0.2$; light violet – $V_{\text{red}} = 1.0$, *two left panels*. Total bound number of stars as a function of their pericenter for different reduction V_{red} . Orbital elements e_{orb} vs. a_{orb} for the stars as a function of their GalC passage time, *two right panels*.